

On Generalized Quasi-Kenmotsu Manifolds

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Abstract: We present a brief analysis on some properties of generalized quasi-Sasakian manifolds, discuss some important properties, particularly, regard the integrability conditions of this kind of manifolds in this paper.

Key Words: Riemannian manifold, semi-Riemannian manifold, quasi-Sasakian structure, integrability.

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§1. Introduction

An interesting topic in the differential geometry is the theory of submanifolds in space endowed with additional structures ([5], [6]). Cr-submanifolds of Kaehler manifolds were studied by A.Bejancu, B.Y.Chen, N.Papaghiuc etc. have studied semi-invariant submanifolds in Sasakian manifolds ([1], [9]). The notion of Kenmotsu manifolds was defined by K.Kenmotsu in 1972 ([10]). N.Papaghiuc have studied semi-invariant submanifolds in a Kenmotsu manifold ([11]). He also studied the geometry of leaves on a semi-invariant ξ^\perp -submanifolds in a Kenmotsu manifolds ([12]).

§2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 An $(2n + 1)$ -dimensional semi-Riemannian manifold (\tilde{M}, \tilde{g}) is said to be an indefinite almost contact manifold if it admits an indefinite almost contact structure (ϕ, ξ, η) , where ϕ is a tensor field of type $(1, 1)$, ξ is a vector field and η is a 1-form, satisfying

$$\phi^2 X = -X + \eta(X)\xi, \quad \eta \circ \phi = 0, \quad \phi\xi = 0, \quad \eta(\xi) = 1, \quad (2.1)$$

$$\tilde{g}(\phi X, \phi Y) = \tilde{g}(X, Y) - \epsilon\eta(X)\eta(Y), \quad (2.2)$$

$$\tilde{g}(X, \xi) = \epsilon\eta(X), \quad (2.3)$$

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$$\tilde{g}(\phi X, \phi Y) = \tilde{g}(X, Y) - \eta(X)\eta(Y) \quad (2.4)$$

for all vector fields X, Y on \tilde{M} and where $\epsilon = \tilde{g}(\xi, \xi) = \pm 1$ and $\tilde{\nabla}$ is the Levi-Civita (L-C) connection for a semi-Riemannian metric \tilde{g} . Let $F(\tilde{M})$ be the algebra of the smooth functions on \tilde{M} .

Definition 2.2 An almost contact manifold $\tilde{M}(\phi, \xi, \eta)$ is said to be normal if

$$N_\phi(X, Y) + 2d\eta(X, Y)\xi = 0$$

where

$$N_\phi(X, Y) = [\phi X, \phi Y] + \phi^2[X, Y] - \phi[\phi X, Y] - \phi[X, \phi Y] \quad X, Y \in \Gamma(T\tilde{M})$$

is the nijenhuis tensor field corresponding to the tensor fields ϕ . The fundamental 2-form Φ on \tilde{M} is defined by

$$\Phi(X, Y) = \tilde{g}(X, \phi Y).$$

In [7]-[8], the authors studied hypersurfaces of an almost contact metric manifold \tilde{M} . In this paper we define hypersurfaces of an almost contact metric manifold \tilde{M} whose structure tensor field satisfy the following relation

$$(\tilde{\nabla}_X \phi)Y = \tilde{g}(\tilde{\nabla}_{\phi^2 X} \xi, Y)\xi - \eta(Y)\tilde{\nabla}_{\phi^2 X} \xi, \quad (2.5)$$

where $\tilde{\nabla}$ is the Levi-Civita connection of the metric tensor \tilde{g} . We name this manifold \tilde{M} equipped with an almost contact metric structure satisfying from (2.5) as generalized Quasi-Kenmotsu manifold, in short G.Q.K.

We define a $(1, 1)$ tensor field F by

$$FX = \tilde{\nabla}_X \xi. \quad (2.6)$$

Let us now state the following proposition:

Proposition 2.1 If \tilde{M} is a G.Q.K manifold then any integral curve of the structure vector field ξ is a geodesic i.e. $\tilde{\nabla}_\xi \xi = 0$. Again $d\Phi = 0$ iff ξ is a Killing vector field.

Proof From equation (2.5) putting $X = Y = \xi$ we can easily prove this assertion.

Next, we derive

$$\begin{aligned} 3d\Phi(X, Y, Z) &= \tilde{g}((\tilde{\nabla}_X \phi)Z, Y) + \tilde{g}((\tilde{\nabla}_Z \phi)Y, X) + \tilde{g}((\tilde{\nabla}_Y \phi)X, Z) \\ &\quad + \eta(X)(\tilde{g}(Y, \tilde{\nabla}_{\phi Z} \xi) + \tilde{g}(\phi Z, \tilde{\nabla}_Y \xi)) \\ &\quad + \eta(Y)(\tilde{g}(Z, \tilde{\nabla}_{\phi X} \xi) + \tilde{g}(\phi X, \tilde{\nabla}_Z \xi)) \\ &\quad + \eta(Z)(\tilde{g}(X, \tilde{\nabla}_{\phi Y} \xi) + \tilde{g}(\phi Y, \tilde{\nabla}_X \xi)) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, if ξ is a killing vector field then $d\Phi = 0$.

Conversely, Suppose $d\Phi = 0$. taking into account $X = \xi, \eta(Y) = \eta(Z) = 0$, the last equation implies

$$\tilde{g}(Y, \tilde{\nabla}_{\phi Z}\xi) + \tilde{g}(\phi Z, \tilde{\nabla}_Y\xi) = 0$$

Now substituting $Z = \phi Z$ and $Y = Y - \eta(Y)\xi$ we get,

$$\tilde{g}(Y - \eta(Y)\xi, \tilde{\nabla}_{\phi^2 Z}\xi) + \tilde{g}(\phi^2 Z, \tilde{\nabla}_{Y - \eta(Y)\xi}\xi) = 0$$

This implies ξ is a killing vector field. □

Let \tilde{M} be a G.Q.K manifold and considering an m -dimensional submanifold M , isometrically immersed in \tilde{M} . Assuming g, ∇ , are the induced metric and levi-Civita connvection on M respectively. Let ∇^\perp and h be the normal connection induced by $\tilde{\nabla}$ on the normal bundle TM^\perp and the second fundamental form of M , respectively.

Therefore, we can decompose the tangent bundle as

$$T\tilde{M} = TM \oplus TM^\perp.$$

The Gauss and Weingarten formulae are characterized by the equations

$$\tilde{\nabla}_X Y = \nabla_X Y + h(X, Y), \tag{2.7}$$

$$\tilde{\nabla}_X N = -A_N X + \nabla_X^\perp N, \tag{2.8}$$

where A_N is the Weingarten map w.r.t the normal section N and satisfies

$$g(A_N X, Y) = g(h(X, Y), N) \quad X, Y \in \Gamma(TM), N \in \Gamma(TM^\perp). \tag{2.9}$$

Now we shall give the definition of semi-invariant ξ^\perp -submanifold. According to Bejancu ([4]) M is a semi-invariant ξ^\perp -submanifold if there exists two orthogonal distributions, D and D^\perp in TM such that

$$TM = D \oplus D^\perp, \phi D = D, \phi D^\perp \subset TM^\perp, \tag{2.10}$$

where \oplus denotes the orthogonal sum.

If $D^\perp = \{0\}$, then M is an invariant ξ^\perp -submanifold. The normal bundle can also be decomposed as

$$TM^\perp = \phi D^\perp \oplus \mu,$$

where $\phi\mu \subset \mu$. Hence μ contains ξ .

§3. Integrability of Distributions on a Semi-Invariant ξ^\perp -Submanifolds

Let M be a semi-invariant ξ^\perp -submanifold of a G.Q.K manifold \tilde{M} . We denote by P and Q the projections of TM on D and D^\perp respectively, namely for any $X \in \Gamma(TM)$.

$$X = PX + QX, \tag{3.1}$$

Again, for any $X \in \Gamma(TM)$ and $N \in \Gamma(TM^\perp)$ we put

$$\phi X = tX + \omega X, \quad (3.2)$$

$$\phi N = BN + CN, \quad (3.3)$$

with $tX \in \Gamma(D)$, $BN \in \Gamma(TM)$ and $\omega X, CN \in \Gamma(TM^\perp)$. Again, for $X \in \Gamma(TM)$, the decomposition is

$$FX = \alpha X + \beta X, \alpha X \in \Gamma(D), \beta X \in \Gamma(TM^\perp). \quad (3.4)$$

This section deals with the study of the integrability of both distributions D and D^\perp . We have the following proposition:

Proposition 3.1 *Let M be a semi-invariant ξ^\perp -submanifold of a G.Q.K manifold \tilde{M} . Then we obtain*

$$(\nabla_X t)Y = A_{\omega Y}X + Bh(X, Y) \quad (3.5a)$$

$$(\nabla_X \omega)Y = Ch(X, Y) - h(X, tY) - g(FX, Y)\xi. \quad (3.5b)$$

Proof Notice that

$$\begin{aligned} (\tilde{\nabla}_X \phi)YZ &= -\phi \tilde{\nabla}_X Y + \tilde{\nabla}_X \phi Y \\ &= -\phi(\nabla_X Y + h(X, Y)) + \tilde{\nabla}_X tY + \tilde{\nabla}_X \omega Y. \end{aligned}$$

Using (3.3) and (3.4) and the Gauss and Weingarten formula we get

$$(\tilde{\nabla}_X \phi)Y = (-t\nabla_X Y + \nabla_X tY) + (-\omega\nabla_X Y + \nabla_X^\perp \omega Y) - Bh(X, Y) - Ch(X, Y) + h(X, tY) - A_{\omega Y}X.$$

After some brief calculations we deduce

$$(\tilde{\nabla}_X \phi)Y = (\nabla_X t)Y + (\nabla_X \omega)Y - Bh(X, Y) - Ch(X, Y) + h(X, tY) - A_{\omega Y}X.$$

Again,

$$(\tilde{\nabla}_X \phi)Y = \tilde{g}(\tilde{\nabla}_{\phi^2 X} \xi, Y)\xi - \eta(Y)\tilde{\nabla}_{\phi^2 X} \xi,$$

Using (2.1) and some steps of calculations, we obtain

$$(\tilde{\nabla}_X \phi)Y = -g(\tilde{\nabla}_X \xi, Y)\xi,$$

as $(\eta(Y) = 0, g(\xi, Y) = 0$ as $\xi \perp D, D^\perp$). Hence,

$$(\tilde{\nabla}_X \phi)Y = -g(FX, Y)\xi.$$

On comparing the tangential and normal components we shall obtain the results. \square

Taking into the consideration the decomposition of TM^\perp , we can prove that:

Proposition 3.2 *Let M be a semi-invariant ξ^\perp -submanifold of a G.Q.K manifold \tilde{M} . Then for any $N \in \Gamma(TM^\perp)$, there are*

- (1) $BN \in D^\perp$;
- (2) $CN \in \mu$.

Proof Let $N \in \Gamma(TM^\perp)$,

$$\phi N = BN + CN,$$

We know $TM^\perp = \phi D^\perp \oplus \mu$. Therefore we have

$$BN \in \phi D^\perp \subseteq D^\perp, CN \in \mu. \quad \square$$

Proposition 3.3 *Let M be a semi-invariant ξ^\perp -submanifold of a G.Q.K manifold \tilde{M} , then*

$$A_{\omega X}Y = A_{\omega Y}X,$$

for any $X, Y \in \Gamma(TM^\perp)$.

Proof From equation (2.9) we have

$$\begin{aligned} g(A_{\omega X}Y, Z) &= g(h(Y, Z), \omega X) = g(\tilde{\nabla}_Z Y, \omega X) \\ &= -g(\omega \tilde{\nabla}_Z Y, X) = g(\omega Y, h(Z, X)) \\ &= g(h(X, Z), \omega Y) = g(A_{\omega Y}X, Z). \end{aligned}$$

Hence the result. □

Proposition 3.4 *Let M be a semi-invariant ξ^\perp -submanifold of a G.Q.K manifold \tilde{M} . Then the distribution D^\perp is integrable.*

Proof Let $Z, X \in \Gamma(D^\perp)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_Z tX &= (\nabla_Z t)X + t\nabla_Z X \\ \nabla_Z tX &= A_{X\omega}Z + Bh(Z, X) + t\nabla_Z X. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, (i)

$$t\nabla_Z X = \nabla_Z tX - A_{\omega X}Z - Bh(X, Z)$$

Interchanging X and Z we have (ii)

$$t\nabla_X Z = \nabla_X tZ - A_{\omega Z}X - Bh(Z, X).$$

Subtracting equation (ii) from (i) and using Proposition (3.3), we obtain

$$t([Z, X]) = \nabla_Z tX - \nabla_X tZ. \quad \square$$

Theorem 3.1 *If M is a semi-invariant ξ^\perp -submanifold of a G.Q.K manifold \tilde{M} , then the*

distribution D is integrable if and only if

$$h(Z, tW) - h(W, tZ) = (\mathbf{L}_\xi \tilde{g})(Z, W)\xi, \quad X, Y \in \Gamma(D).$$

Proof From the covariant derivative we have

$$\nabla_Z \omega W = (\tilde{\nabla}_Z \omega W) + \omega \nabla_Z W,$$

$$\nabla_Z \omega W = Ch(Z, W) - h(Z, tW) - g(FZ, W)\xi + \omega(\nabla_Z W + h(Z, W))$$

for $Z, W \in \Gamma(D)$. Again using Weingarten formulae we have

$$\nabla_Z \omega W = -A_{\omega W} Z + \nabla_Z^\perp \omega W.$$

Comparing both the equations we get

$$-A_{\omega W} Z + \nabla_Z^\perp \omega W = Ch(Z, W) - h(Z, tW) - g(FZ, W)\xi + \omega(\nabla_Z W + h(Z, W)).$$

On a simplification we obtain

$$\omega \nabla_W Z = \nabla_Z^\perp \omega W - A_{\omega W} Z - Ch(Z, W) + h(W, tZ) - g(FW, Z)\xi.$$

Interchanging W and Z in the above equation, we get

$$\omega \nabla_Z W = \nabla_W^\perp \omega Z - A_{\omega Z} W - Ch(W, Z) + h(Z, tW) - g(FZ, W)\xi.$$

Subtracting the above two equations and using Proposition 3.3 we get

$$\omega[Z, W] = h(Z, tW) - h(W, tZ) - g(FZ, W)\xi + g(FW, Z)\xi.$$

We also know that

$$(\mathbf{L}_\xi \tilde{g})(Z, W)\xi = g(FZ, W)\xi - g(FW, Z)\xi.$$

Therefore the distribution D is integrable if

$$h(Z, tW) - h(W, tZ) = (\mathbf{L}_\xi \tilde{g})(Z, W)\xi. \quad \square$$

Proposition 3.5 *Let M be a semi-invariant ξ^\perp -submanifold of a $G.Q.K$ manifold \tilde{M} . Then $\alpha X = A_\xi X$ and $\beta X = -\nabla_X^\perp \xi$ $X \in \Gamma(TM)$.*

Proof From Weingarten formulae we get

$$\tilde{\nabla}_X \xi = -A_\xi X + \nabla_X^\perp \xi.$$

Again we know from (3.4),

$$\tilde{\nabla}_X \xi = -FX = -\alpha X - \beta X.$$

Comparing these formulae we get $\alpha X = A_\xi X$ and $\beta X = -\nabla_X^\perp \xi$ by assuming

$$\{e_i, \phi e_i, e_{2p+j}\}, i = \{1, \dots, p\}, j = \{1, \dots, q\}$$

being an adapted orthonormal local frame on M , where $q = \dim D^\perp$ and $2p = \dim D$. □

Similarly, the following theorem is obtained.

Theorem 3.2 *If M is a ξ^\perp -semiinvariant submanifold of a G.Q.K manifold \tilde{M} one has*

$$\eta(H) = \frac{1}{m} \text{trace} (A_\xi); m = 2p + q.$$

Proof From the mean curvature formula

$$H = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{a=1}^s \text{trace}(A_{\xi_a}) \xi_a,$$

where $\{\xi_1, \dots, \xi_s\}$ is an orthonormal basis in TM^\perp ,

$$\eta(H) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{a=1}^s \text{trace}(A_{\xi_a}) \cdot 1,$$

$$\eta(H) = \frac{1}{m} \text{trace}(A_\xi). \quad \square$$

Corollary 3.1 *If the leaves of the integrable distribution D are totally geodesic in M then the structures vector field ξ is D -killing, i.e. $(\mathbf{L}_\xi g)(X, Y) = 0, X, Y \in \Gamma(D)$.*

Proof We know that

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{L}_\xi g)(X, Y) &= g(\nabla_X \xi, Y) + g(X, \nabla_Y \xi) \\ &= g(\nabla_X Y, \xi) + g(\xi, \nabla_Y X) = 0, \quad X, Y \in \Gamma(D). \end{aligned}$$

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